

Effect of NaBH₄ Loading and Reduction Temperature on Defect-Driven CO₂ Photoreduction over TiO₂

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SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS

1. Experimental section

Figure S1. Images of the prepared TiO₂-based photocatalyst samples: B-TiO₂_350°C_0.75 (a), B-TiO₂_350°C_1.5 (b), B-TiO₂_350°C_2.0 (c), B-TiO₂_500°C_1.5 (d), B-TiO₂_650°C_1.5 (e), and W-TiO₂_350°C (f).

1.1. Photocatalytic CO₂ reduction experiments

Photocatalytic experiments were conducted in a batch-stirred photoreactor (volume 348 ml, Figure S2). Photocatalytic experiments were carried out in the presence of a reaction mixture containing 100 ml of 0.2 M NaOH with 0.1 g of a powder photocatalyst sample. The reactor was thoroughly closed, and the mixture was saturated by CO₂ to purge the air from the reactor. The reaction was conducted under ambient temperature conditions (30 ± 1 °C) without external heating or cooling. The reaction mixture was stirred at 350 rpm. The irradiation source was an 8 W UVC ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 254$ nm) pen-ray lamp, with a light intensity of approximately 5.0

$\text{mW}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ (as specified by the manufacturer, Ultra-Violet Products Inc., Germany). This lamp was placed on a quartz glass window at the top of the photoreactor. Before the start of the reaction, the reactor was sealed, and a sample of the gaseous phase was taken through the septum by syringe. Subsequently, the gaseous samples were analyzed using a gas chromatograph (GC, Shimadzu Tracera GC-2010PLUS) equipped with a BID detector (dielectric barrier discharge ionization detector). The reaction mixture was irradiated for 7 hours. Samples of the gaseous phase were taken at 2, 4, 6, and 7 hours for analysis on the GC-BID device. All experiments were repeated to ensure reproducible results. H_2 , CO , and CH_4 were detected as the main products of realized experiments. The stability of the photocatalysts was validated by repeated use of the same batch with reproducible results.

Figure S2. Batch photoreactor for the photocatalytic reduction of CO_2 .

1.2. Characterization of the prepared defect-based TiO_2 photocatalyst samples

Phase composition and microstructural properties were determined using X-ray powder diffraction (XRD) technique. XRD patterns were obtained using Rigaku SmartLab diffractometer (Rigaku, Tokyo, Japan) with detector D/teX Ultra 250. The source of X-ray irradiation was Cu tube ($\text{CuK}\alpha$, $\lambda_1 = 0.154059 \text{ nm}$, $\lambda_2 = 0.154441 \text{ nm}$) operated at 40 kV and 30 mA. Incident and diffracted beam optics were equipped with 5° Soller slits; incident slits were set up to value 1 mm. Slits on the diffracted beam were set up to fixed value 1 and 1 mm. The powder samples were gently grinded using agate mortar before analysis and pressed using microscope glass in rotational sample holder and measured in the reflection mode (Bragg-Brentano geometry). The samples rotated (30 rpm) during the measurement to eliminate preferred orientation effect. The XRD patterns were collected in a 2θ range $5^\circ - 90^\circ$ with a step size of 0.01° and speed $0.5 \text{ deg}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$. Measured XRD patterns were evaluated using PDXL 2 software (version 2.4.2.0, Rigaku, Tokyo, Japan) and compared with database PDF-2, release 2015 (ICDD, Newton Square, USA).

The Raman spectra were obtained by the dispersive Raman spectrometer DXR SmartRaman (ThermoScientific, USA), using a 532 nm excitation laser. The exposure time during this measurement was 1 s, and the number of repetitions per measurement was 1000.

For microscopic examination, catalysts were ground into a fine powder in an agate mortar. The resulting powder of each catalyst was poured into 99.8% ethanol (POCH, Poland) to form a slurry, which was then subjected to ultrasonic homogenization for 10 s. The suspensions of the catalyst powders in ethanol (99.8%, POCH, Poland) were applied to 200-mesh copper grids covered with carbon-stabilized lace formvar (Ted Pella Company, USA) and left on a filter paper until the ethanol evaporated. The copper grids with the applied samples were placed in a single-tilt holder and transferred to the electron microscope. The analysis of catalyst samples was performed using a high-resolution electron microscope, the Titan G2 60–300 kV (FEI company, Netherlands). The main equipment of the microscope included a field emission gun (FEG), a monochromator, a three condenser lens system, an objective lens system, image correction (Cs-corrector), an HAADF detector and an EDS (Energy-Dispersive X-Ray Spectroscopy) spectrometer with a Si(Li) detector. Microscopic measurements of the samples were performed at an accelerating voltage of 300 kV.

X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS) measurements were carried out with the 128 channel Argus hemispherical X-ray photoelectron spectrometer (Omicron NanoTechnology) with pass energy 40 eV. The Mg- $K\alpha$ X-ray source was operated at 15 keV, 300 W. XPS measurements were conducted under ultra-high vacuum at room temperature, with pressure below 1.1×10^{-8} mbar. Recorded spectra were processed and deconvoluted with the CASA XPS software package. The Shirley background subtraction and the Gauss-Lorentz curve (GL 30) were used for fitting. Spectra were calibrated to obtain a binding energy of 285.00 eV for C 1s line.

The Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) surface area and pore volumes of the materials were determined by the on the basis of the adsorption/desorption isotherms performed on a QUADRASORB evo™ Gas Sorption analyzer (Anton Paar GmbH, Austria, previously Quantachrome Instruments, USA) at 77 K. Prior to analysis the materials were degassed at 373 K for 16 h under a high vacuum using the MasterPrep sample degassing system (Anton Paar GmbH, Austria). The Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (SBET) equation was used to determine the surface area. The total pore volume (TPV) was calculated from the volume of nitrogen after pore condensation at a relative pressure ($p/p_0 = 0.99$). The volume of micropores (V_{micro}) was estimated by the Dubinin-Radushkevich method. The mesopore volume (V_{meso}) was calculated from the difference of the TPV and the V_{micro} .

Electrochemical measurements were conducted using a photoelectric spectrometer (Instytut Fotonowy, Poland) in a three-electrode configuration. The working electrode consisted of the photocatalyst material, while Ag/AgCl electrode served as the reference electrode, and a platinum wire acted as the counter electrode. A $0.1 \text{ mol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ KNO_3 solution (pH = 6.1) was used as the electrolyte. Prior to measurement, the electrolyte was purged with argon for 15 minutes to remove dissolved oxygen, and a constant argon flow was maintained throughout the experiment. Photocurrents were recorded by front-side irradiation of the working electrode with a 150 W xenon lamp. The wavelength of the incident light was controlled by a monochromator and varied from 250 to 450 nm in 10 nm increments. Voltages ranging from -0.2 to 1.0 V (vs Ag/AgCl) were applied. The irradiated surface area of the working electrode was 0.785 cm^2 , as determined by the 1.0 cm diameter of the illumination window.

2. Results and Discussion

Figure S3. Time dependence of H₂, CO, and CH₄ yields during CO₂ photoreduction over B-TiO₂ photocatalysts prepared at 350 °C with varied amounts of NaBH₄ (a – c) and synthesized samples with 1.5 g of NaBH₄ and different reduction temperatures (d – f), with error bars represent 5% measurement error.

Figure S4. O 1s XPS spectra of the synthesized B-TiO₂-based photocatalysts and the reference W-TiO₂_350°C sample.

Table S1. Quantitative analysis of oxygen fractions from XPS measurements of the investigated photocatalyst samples.

Sample	O 1s		
	O _{Ti-O} ^a (%)	O _v ^b (%)	O _{O-H} ^c (%)
B-TiO ₂ _350°C_0.75	68	23	9
B-TiO ₂ _350°C_1.5	61	25	14
B-TiO ₂ _350°C_2.0	57	24	19
B-TiO ₂ _500°C_1.5	52	28	20
B-TiO ₂ _650°C_1.5	46	26	28
W-TiO ₂ _350°C	76	18	6

^a ... lattice oxygen (O_{Ti-O})

^b ... oxygen vacancies (O_v)

^c ... O-H groups (O_{O-H})

Figure S5. Ti 2p XPS spectra of the synthesized B-TiO₂-based photocatalysts and the reference W-TiO₂_350°C sample.

Figure S6. N₂ adsorption/desorption isotherms of (a) B-TiO₂ reduced at 350 °C with 0.75, 1.5, and 2.0 g of NaBH₄ reductant, (b) B-TiO₂ reduced at 350 °C, 500 °C, and 650 °C with 1.5 g of NaBH₄ reducing agent, (c) comparison between the most active B-TiO₂-based sample, B-TiO₂_350°C_1.5, and the prepared reference sample W-TiO₂_350°C.

Figure S7. Photocurrent generation at different wavelengths and applied potential 1 V with 5 s open/close shutter for (a) B-TiO₂ reduced at 350 °C with 0.75, 1.5, and 2.0 g of NaBH₄ reductant, (b) B-TiO₂ reduced at 350 °C, 500 °C, and 650 °C with 1.5 g of NaBH₄ reducing agent, (c) comparison between the B-TiO₂_350°C_1.5, and the prepared reference sample W-TiO₂_350°C.

Figure S8. Photocurrent generation at applied potential 1 V and wavelength 350 nm with 30 s open/close shutter for (a) B-TiO₂ reduced at 350 °C with 0.75, 1.5, and 2.0 g of NaBH₄ reductant, (b) B-TiO₂ reduced at 350 °C, 500 °C, and 650 °C with 1.5 g of NaBH₄ reducing agent, (c) comparison between the most active B-TiO₂-based sample, B-TiO₂_350°C_1.5, and the reference sample W-TiO₂_350°C.

Figure S9. Time dependence of H₂, CO, and CH₄ yields during CO₂ photoreduction over the most active defect-based sample B-TiO₂_350°C_1.5 (a) and reference samples W-TiO₂_350°C (b) and commercial TiO₂ – P25 (c), with error bars represent 5% measurement error.